

SWeaT ASIC Run 1

Technical Documentation

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STATUS

EUROPRACTICE mini@sic: UMC L180 Mixed-Mode/RF.

GDS submitted: 30/07/2021. (IMEC in: 03/08/2021).

Chip delivery: 10/02/2022.

R1 (run 1): due to failure of digital cells replacement at IMEC, the chip functionalities resulted extremely impaired. For detailed information about performed tests see the “Electrical tests” of this document. A new version (R2) is planned for resubmission at the end of July 2022.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Operating conditions

- External supplies need to be provided. For minimal operation 0.9V for both analog and digital core and 1.8V for pad ESD and SPI digital wire SDO.
- From the communication point of with the ASIC behaves like a slave, thus a Microcontroller is needed to provide commands and/or bridging the communication with a PC.
- System clock is provided by an internal relaxation oscillator, however can be forced externally through a dedicated pad.

Interfacing sensors characteristics

The ASIC performs:

- Time-interleaved high-impedance potentiometric digital readout (ISE/REF chemical sensing) on 4 channels by dedicated per-channel low-power unity-gain buffering to a switched-capacitors Delta-Sigma ADC;
- Input impedance buffering provided by two selectable modalities: even chopper modulated unity-gain buffering (CHS) or ping-pong auto-zeroed unity-gain OpAmps (PPAZ);
- Capacitance readout based on iterative delay-chain readout with internal compensation of offset and temperature sensitivity;
- VPTAT source and its routing to the ADC for external temperature compensation of the sensors.

Top schematic

Test blocks: MOS and R/FC are totally independent from the SWeaT core circuitry. These blocks are intended for testing purposes.

Description of the blocks

FSM

Digital Finite-State Machine equipped with SPI interface (slave).

ADC S/A (stand alone)

Single-Bit with 3-stage FIR filtered digital feedback Delta-Sigma Modulator.

CHS S/A (stand alone)

Chopper-stabilised high-input-impedance OpAmp with ripple-cancellation feedback.

CDC+CDC/D (dummy)

Capacitance-to-digital converter (including the dummy replica for internal CREF sensing) based on iterative-delay chain conversion principle¹.

OSC

Ultra-low power relaxation oscillator.

REF1

All-MOS² current and voltage references.

REF2

As REF1, but with better VPTAT characteristics.

CHS(x5)

As CHS S/A: 5 channels of which 4 dedicated to potentiometric sensor readout and one is dedicated to internal VPTAT readout (from REF2). The chopper-stabilised operational amplifier is inspired by the topology Kusuda's work³.

AZ(x5)

Ping-pong autozeroed OpAmps (4 for potentiometric readout and one for internal VPTAT) for driving performance, in case external ADC is used. These channels can be turned off by grounding their dedicated supply: VDD_CH_AZ.

ADC

Single-Bit with 3-stage FIR filtered digital feedback Delta-Sigma Modulator (as ADC S/A).

¹ MDPI Sensors 2022, 22, 121. doi: 10.3390/s22010121

² IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, vol. 38, no. 1, pp. 84-88, Jan. 2003, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2002.806258.

³ IEEE Journal of Solid-State Circuits, vol. 45, no. 8, pp. 1436-1445, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1109/JSSC.2010.2048142.

R/FC

N/D.

MOS

N/D.

ADC-modulator spectra

Nominal electrical simulations in standard configuration, Spectre.

Chip microphotograph

Pads

Table 1: Power breakdown by blocksColor code for positioning on floorplan: **up: yellow; right: red; bottom: green; left: cyan**; Shaded cells indicate autonomous test structures.

Pin name	Type	Nominal value	Description
vdd_chs_ota	inout	0.9 V	VDD DOMAINS: S/A CHS OTA
vdd_dig	inout	>= 0.9 V	VDD DOMAINS: FSM and AUX
vddl	inout	0.5 V	VDD DOMAINS: CDC voltage reference
vddh	inout	0.9 V	VDD DOMAINS: CDC voltage reference
vdd_io	inout	1.8 V	VDD DOMAINS: I/O pads
vdd_osc	inout	0.9 V	VDD DOMAINS: internal oscillator
vdd_refs	inout	0.9 V	VDD DOMAINS: internal references
VDD_DS_PAD	inout	0.9 V	Supplies the S/A ADC. For its streamout however, vdd_dig needs to be provided (as for the output buffer).
VDD_CH_AZ	inout	0.9 V	Supplies the AZ(x5) channels. To be grounded if unused.
VDD_CH_CHS	inout	0.9 V	Supplies the CHS(x5) channels+channel ADC and the Reference block for the S/A ADC. (Also cmd_dig for RC/RFC: if 0V FC, else 1.8V RFC)
gnd1	inout		Ground
nCS_IN	in		SPI/DIG
SCL_IN	in		
SDL_IN	in		
SDO_OUT	out		
reset_pad	inout		Nominally left as floating. Force to gnd for external hard reset
int_clock_pad	out		CLOCKS
ext_clock	in	1.8 V level, 12 kHz	
vo	out		CHS_STAND-ALONE
vin	in		
vip	in		
BULK_DS_PAD	in	<= VDD_DS_PAD	ADC_STAND-ALONE
IN_DS_PAD	in		
CLK_DS_SA_PAD	out	3 kHz nominal	
BITSTREAM_DS_SA	out		S/A ADC bitstream output
vcSENS	in	40 pF nominal cap fullscale	CDC input sensing capacitance terminal
IN_CH1_AZ	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 1, AZ buffering
IN_CH2_AZ	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 2, AZ buffering
IN_CH3_AZ	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 3, AZ buffering
IN_CH4_AZ	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 4, AZ buffering
IN_CH1_CHS	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 1, CHS buffering
IN_CH2_CHS	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 2, CHS buffering
IN_CH3_CHS	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 3, CHS buffering
IN_CH4_CHS	in		potentiometric CHANNEL 4, CHS buffering
out_ch_az	out		
BISTREAM_DS_CH	out		
VREF_PAD	inout		Also valid for ADC S/A
vdd_bg	inout	Internal pad	EXTRA-BG
vref	inout	Internal pad	
Source1	inout	Internal pad	
Source2	inout	Internal pad	
Drain1	inout	Internal pad	
vdd_fc_rfc	inout	1.8 V nominal	EXTRA-FCRFC
vin+_fc_rfc	in		
vin-_fc_rfc	in		
clk_fc_rfc	in	1.8 V level, 100 kHz	
out+_fc_rfc	out		
out-_fc_rfc	out		
vbn	in		bias FC/RFC (input to an NMOS, diode connected)

Bonding diagram

Chip bonding diagram in a J-Leaded Ceramic Chip Carrier (JLCC) ceramic package with 44 leads.

SWeaT

SYSTEM CONFIGURATIONS

DIG_CDC

Conversion started by command: PRE_CDC & PRE_CDC_DUMMY. Detailed circuit description in “Cicalini, M.; Piotto, M.; Bruschi, P.; Dei, M. Design of a Capacitance-to-Digital Converter Based on Iterative Delay-Chain Discharge in 180 nm CMOS Technology. Sensors 2022, 22, 121. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s22010121>”

ADC

Clock frequencies:

<i>Ck</i>	1	0 (default)	2	3
<i>Frequency [kHz]</i>	1.5	3.0	6.0	12.0

FSM registers

ANA_CONFIG1

(default: 0h1101):

15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8
cfg_AZ		CDC_SEL	PRE_CDC_D UMMY	CFG_CDC_DUMMY			CKE (def: 1)

7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
DIV_CHS		ACFB_EN	CHS_EN	CFG_BIAS		CFG_CDC	PRE_CDC

- **cfg_AZ**: unity-gain auto-zero buffers bias
- **CDC_SEL**: capacitance-to-digital converter selection, 0: sensing vcsens, 1: dummy
- **PRE_CDC_DUMMY**: 0: precharge, 1: start conversion
- **CKE**: External clock configuration; 0: FSM does not produce clock
- **DIV_CHS**: CHS clock configuration. 00: 500Hz, 01: 1000Hz, 10: 1500Hz, 11: 2000Hz.
- **ACFB_EN**: CHS auto-correction feedback enable
- **CHS_EN**: CHS enable
- **CFG_BIAS**: CHS bias configuration
- **CFG_CDC**: main CDC. 0: vcsens, 1: internal cap for calibration
- **PRE_CDC**: 0: precharge, 1: start conversion

ANA_CONFIG2

(default: 0h0080):

15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8
OSR	cha_AZ			cha_main			CHA_SEL

7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
RESET_ADC (def: 1)	ADC_SEL	ADC_CLK_DIV		OSC_TRIM			

- **OSR**: CIC configuration: 0: 512, 1: 256.
- **cha_AZ**: AZ-channel mux selector (if >4, vptat)
- **cha_main**: CHS-channel mux selector (if >4, vptat)
- **CHA_SEL**: mux of cha_AZ and cha_main outputs. 1: cha_main, 0: cha_AZ
- **RESET_ADC**: ADC reset signal (active low, default 1).
- **ADC_SEL**: bitstream selector (0: mux, 1: stand-alone)
- **ADC_CLK_DIV**: ADC clock configurations (see table above).
- **OSC_TRIM**: internal oscillator trimming against corners variations

ANA_CONFIG3

(default: X0):

15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
															E_nI

- **E_nI**: clock enable, 1: external, 0: internal (default)

ADC_READ

(read only): stores the conversion result.

COMMAND REG

The command register is used to assert one-shot commands.

List of commands:

- X10: system reset
- X30: CDC counters' reset
- X40: ADC single read

POWER CONSUMPTION BREAKDOWN

Depending on the specific block, power consumption needs different descriptors reflecting the operating conditions and with the aim to correctly identify the specific function of the SoC. For instance the FSM may present high impulsive current consumption while being interrogated by the SPI communication port. Similarly, the CDC also has high demanding peaks while operating the capacitance conversion. On the other hand, most of the rest of analog blocks present a dominant static power consumption. Hence in the case of digital-intensive blocks, there is a need to report not only the peak power consumption but also the average power consumption together with the operating time. In the latter case the total energy per specific function can be easily obtained. This characterization need arises when the SoC is to be operated by limited power/energy sources that can be implemented by external energy harvesters (i.e. Biofuelcells –BFCs– or Thermoelectric Generators – TEGs –).

Table 2: Power breakdown by blocks

Block	Static Power	Averaged Peak Power in operating time	Operating time	Notes
FSM	[Estimated] 66uW*3*8*1ns/120ns = 13.2uW (when continuously interrogated through SPI)	66uW@1.8 VDD (I/O) [Data from mixed-signal simulation output]	3*8/200e6 = 120ns	FSM clock is 12kHz. Power is peaked while interrogated by the SPI master. Peak power duration is estimated as 1ns. I2C parameters: fck=200kHz, 3 bytes communication packet. Energy per communication packet: 1.584 pJ
CDC+ CDC/D	[Estimated] 85.2pJ/133us=641nW (CS=11.3pF). 1.884nJ/2.93ms= 643 nW (CS=250pF)	[From electrical simulations:] 60uA@start conversion (duration 2ns) + counts*12uA (duration 250ps).	133us (CS=11.3pF). 2.93ms (CS=250pF).	Sensors 2022, 22, 121. https://doi.org/10.3390/s22010121
OSC		From 23.85 nW to 32.13 nW (depending on the configuration bits)	Continuous	Current peak: 1.4 uA for 6 us, steady-state: 3 nA
REF1	cfg_AZ=00: nom 316 nW; (ss 275 nW; ff 357 nW) cfg_AZ=11: nom 1.16 uW (ss 1.01 uW; ff 1.31 uW)		Continuous	Depends on cfg_AZ configuration bits, being maximum for 11, and minimum for 00. VDD=0.9V
REF2	nom 199 nW (ss 73 nW; ff 546 nW)		Continuous	
CHS(x5)	cfg_bias=00: 8.7 nW cfg_bias=11:25.5 nW	Peaks of 63uA (4ns duration)	Continuous if selected	[sc_chs_ota] Depends on cfg_bias configuration bits, being maximum for 11, and minimum for 00.
AZ(x5)	cfg_AZ=00: 412 nA (371 nW) cfg_AZ=11: 1.21 uA (1.09 uW)	duplet of peaks of 420uA (1ns duration)	Continuous if selected	[sc_buffer_ppaz] Depends on cfg_AZ configuration bits, being maximum for 11, and minimum for 00. Figures per channel. VDD=0.9V, fck=3kHz
ADC	Clock off: 29.6 nA	Clock on: average power @ 1.5 kHz: 34.69 nW; @ 3 kHz: 37.35 nW	Continuous	Current peaks: 400 uA for 1.1 ns (worst case), regime: 29.6 nA

ELECTRICAL TESTS

1. Power on Reset (PoR) correctly operating after applying VDD.
2. Internal oscillator correctly operating after PoR signal transition.
3. SPI communication test by read/write into the FSM r/w registers: failed.
4. SPI write-only test into the OSC_TRIM bits of ANA_CONFIG2 (internal oscillator configurations): failed, no changes observed in the internal oscillator frequency.

Diagnosis: FSM not present/not responding. Detailed analysis of the ERC/DRC checks log file sent by IMEC upon design submission revealed missing paths to correct Faraday Digital Cells libraries. Due to this, the synthesis of all the digital cells was disrupted and the FSM was not implemented. Unfortunately, the log file didn't raise any ERROR or WARNING.